

Linnæus University

Monthly Report November 2024

SENTINEL Wild Birds

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts.

2. RESULT

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Between August and November 2024, a total of 720 individual birds from 14 different species have been sampled in six countries (four different nodes) around Europe (Table 1). All samples were tested for HPAI. A total of 1101 samples were collected of which 479 were tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 378 cloacal swabs, 155 faeces, 81 feathers, 5 pooled organs, and 3 blood serum. Of all samples, 115 samples (10.4%) were positive for avian influenza of which 19 were positive for HPAI (1.7%; Figure 1; Table 2). All HPAI samples were sampled in Italy between September 24th and October 2nd.

The overall bird-level prevalence of avian influenza in sampled birds in the period was 14.2 %. The highest bird-level prevalence was found in Sweden (29.2 %; Table 1), and the Mallard was the species with most positive tested birds, however, all HPAI samples were found in the Eurasian Teal (Table 1 & 2).

TABLE 1 Total number of individual wild birds sampled (including recaptures of same birds), as well as number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza in the respective country (August-November 2024). The asterisk (*) indicates the HPAI samples.

Group/species	Node 1 Finland		Node 1 Estonia		Node 2 Sweden		Node 2 Poland		Node 6 Austria		Node 7 Italy		Total	
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.
<i>Waterfowl</i>														
Mallard	29	1	33	0	196	61	10	0			1	0	269	62
Eurasian Teal	1	0			84	21					77	18*	162	39
Eurasian Wigeon					1	0							1	0
Greater White-fronted Goose			81	0									81	0
Bean Goose			34	0									34	0
Greylag Goose			2	0									2	0
Barnacle Goose			147	0									147	0
<i>Cormorants</i>														
Great Cormorant					1	0			10	0			11	0
<i>Rails</i>														
Common Moorhen											3	0	3	0
<i>Larids</i>														
Black-headed Gull							4	0	1	0			5	0
Great Black-backed Gull					1	1	1	0					2	1
Lesser Black-backed Gull							1	0					1	0
<i>Waders</i>														
Common Ringed Plover					1	0							1	0
Eurasian Curlew									1	0			1	0
Total	30	1	297	0	284	83	16	0	12	0	81	18	720	102

FIGURE 1 Sample sites for the 720 wild birds sampled in six European countries, yielding 102 samples positive for avian influenza (August-November 2024). The six countries belong to four different nodes: Finland and Estonia Node 1, Sweden and Poland Node 2, Austria Node 6, and Italy Node 7. No samples from Latvia or Lithuania (Node 2), Georgia (Node 4), Germany or Switzerland (Node 6), France (Node 8) or Spain (Node 9) are included in the summary.

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TABLE 2 Total number of collected samples, as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza in the respective country (August-November 2024). The asterisk (*) indicates the HPAI samples.

Group/species	Node 1 Finland			Node 1 Estonia			Node 2 Sweden			Node 2 Poland			Node 6 Austria			Node 7 Italy			Total		
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI
<i>Waterfowl</i>																					
Mallard	58	1	0	33	0	0	315	68	0	10	0	0				3	0	0	419	69	0
Eurasian Teal	2	0	0				143	22	0							231	23	19*	376	45	19
Eurasian Wigeon							2	0	0										2	0	0
Greater White-fronted Goose				81	0	0													81	0	0
Bean Goose				34	0	0													34	0	0
Greylag Goose				2	0	0													2	0	0
Barnacle Goose				147	0	0													147	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																					
Great Cormorant							2	0	0				18	0	0				20	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																					
Common Moorhen																9	0	0	9	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																					
Black-headed Gull										4	0	0	1	0	0				5	0	0
Great Black-backed Gull							2	1	0	1	0	0							3	1	0
Lesser Black-backed Gull										1	0	0							1	0	0
<i>Waders</i>																					
Common Ringed Plover							1	0	0										1	0	0
Eurasian Curlew													1	0	0				1	0	0
Total	60	1	0	297	0	0	465	91	0	16	0	0	20	0	0	243	23	19	1101	115	19

A weekly compilation of all samples (positive and negative) sampled at each node, can be seen in figure 2.

FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of samples collected from week 34 to 45, 2024. A total of 1101 samples (negative samples in blue; positive samples in orange) were collected at four nodes between August and November 2024, yielding 102 samples positive for avian influenza.

2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

To date, a total of five H5 sequences have been deposited in the GISAID EpiFlu from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (N=1) and Node 7 Veneto Region (N=4). They have been combined with a dataset consisting of global representatives of H5 influenza A sequences for genomic analyses. Additionally, 17 non-H5 sequences were also generated by Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea, which were of various subtypes, including H1 (N=6), H2 (N=1), H4 (N=2), H6 (N=1), H7 (N=5), H9 (N=1) and H11 (N=1) avian influenza viruses.

The H5 sequence deposited by Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea was a H5N2, and the haemagglutinin (HA) gene was found to belong to the Eurasian Avian non-Goose Guangdong (EA-nonGsGd) low pathogenicity avian influenza (LPAI) clade. The other viral gene segments were found to be closely related to sequences obtained from Eurasian wild birds and poultry. Whilst most of these sequences also belonged to the EA-nonGsGd clade, there were representatives of HPAI H5 clades, including clade 2.3.4.4b. This is not surprising as the clade 2.3.4.4b has shown a high propensity to reassort with LPAI viruses in recent years resulting in a wide range of different gene constellations.

The sequences deposited by Node 7 Veneto Region were all the H5N1 subtype and demonstrated high similarity to each other. Analysis of the HA gene demonstrated that it belonged to HPAI clade 2.3.4.4b. The other viral gene segments were all found to be closely related to sequences primarily from wild birds collected within Europe, including Austria, France, Slovenia and Italy from October and November 2024. This is consistent with a recent increase in H5N1 HPAI detections within Europe in recent months.

The complete dataset will be made available through the SENTINEL Wild birds Nextstrain groups so that individual users can explore the data.

FIGURE 3 Phylogenetic analyses of the sequences generated by Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea and Node 7 Veneto Region. **A.** Image of the whole HA tree, with the sequences from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (EA-nonGsGd) and Node 7 Veneto Region (HPAIV 2.3.4.4b) highlighted. **B and C.** Zoom images of the HA tree showing the relatives of the sequences from Node 2 and Node 7, respectively.

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3. CONCLUSION

As this is the first summary of collected samples, we refrain from making deeper interpretations of the data at this stage. Nevertheless, all positive samples for HPAI were obtained from Eurasian Teals sampled in the Veneto region in northern Italy at the end of September and the beginning of October. Teals migrate to the region in late autumn and early winter from boreal breeding areas in northern and eastern Europe. They winter in the area in large numbers and have previously been found positive for HPAI. This suggests that the virus is actively circulating within the teal population and the region during this period.